

Supplementary Figure 1. Functional consequences of isoform switches. **(A)** Chart of isoform switch types (<https://www.spandidos-publications.com/10.3892/br.2014.407>). **(B)** Tables presenting isoform switches for each sex group. It is noticeable that females have more observed isoform switches predominantly on γ -IR groups in both age groups while males only have switches in 440 days simGCRsim group. **(C)** Isoform expression of *STOML2* gene at 440 days post-simGCRsim-IR males and post- γ -IR females. It has 1 full-length functional coding, 1 short non-functional, and 1 non-coding long isoforms. At 440 days post-IR, both males exposed to simGCRsim-IR and females exposed to γ -IR showed significantly decreased usage (expression) of *Stoml2* functional isoform.

A

The isoform switch in Cctn2 (Sham vs simGCRsim male 440 days)

B

The isoform switch in Asb2 (Sham vs Gamma female 550 days)

Supplementary Figure 2. Isoform switch plots combine 4 plots and their respective annotation. The top plot represents the structure of the isoforms where thick bars correspond to exons and thin lines to introns (intron sizes are reduced for illustrative purposes). The colors of the exons correspond to the PFAM domain annotation on the right side of the plot. Colors on the top of exons show cellular localization predicted with analyzeDeepLoc2.

Boxplots in the lower part of the plot represent gene and isoform metrics for compared conditions. **A.** Isoform switch of *Cetn2* gene between 440 days male sham and simGCRsim groups. **B.** Isoform switch of *Asb2* gene between 550 days female sham and gamma groups.”